

Modern attitudes to the work of making primary school students interested in reading" or "The content of primary school students' interest in reading

Ilyasova Zamira Uzakbaevna

Assistant of the Department of "General Pedagogy and Psychology" of the Faculty of Primary Education. Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz. Republic of Uzbekistan. The city of Nukus.

Abstract. The article examines the place and role of reading activities in primary school students in the educational process, and recommends a number of effective methods.

Key words: In the educational process, primary education, reading activities, family library, spirituality and enlightenment, book reading, culture, physical education and sports.

Today, in our country, special attention is being paid to increasing the interest of our people, especially the young generation, in reading books, which is of incomparable importance in raising the spiritual-intellectual potential, self-thinking and worldview, in raising a well-rounded person who lives with love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated January 12, 2017 No. F-4789 "On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing interest in book reading and book reading" became the foundation for human spiritual development in our country. . After all, the strength of every country is its educated, intelligent youth who can believe in the future. The main goal of the order is to widely promote reading among

young people, to teach the young generation to read books, in particular, to read fiction, and the main thing is to make them educated and happy.

In the fourth direction of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 76, 2017 PF 4947, entitled "Development of the Social Sector", "ensure the comfort of educational institutions, improve the quality of general secondary, secondary special and higher education" and implementation of measures for their development" is provided. These issues are directly related to the correct solution to the problem of spiritual and moral maturity of young students growing up in our society.

In this regard, special attention is paid to instilling good values and traditions in the life of the society, in particular, to increasing the interest of the young generation in reading books, which is of incomparable importance in raising the spiritual intellectual potential, self-thinking and worldview, in raising a well-rounded person who lives with a sense of love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people. . In this regard, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated September 13, 2017 No. PQ-3271 "On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distribution of book products, to increase and promote interest in book reading and book reading" is the best for development. that books are the factor, that well-chosen books not only make a person educated, but also guarantee happiness, first of all, high-quality printing of books that meet spiritual-educational, artistic-aesthetic requirements, delivery to educational institutions, translation of the best examples of national and world literature recognized the urgent task of forming the reading skills of our young students from childhood, raising the culture of reading in our society.

If we think that books are only a source of knowledge, we will not fully understand its essence. Books actually help young readers to be happy and achieve great heights

in their lives. After all, in any pharmacy, you will not find a drug that will bring a person out of depression and make him strong-willed, patient, and hardworking. But this medicine is a book, in which the reader will find what he is looking for. A book is a source of knowledge, spirituality, and enlightenment. Criteria showing students' interest in reading books. It is appropriate to teach books to students by types. After all, the concept of book culture essentially includes what kind of books to choose, what to read at what age, how to choose additional literature, what kind of knowledge to acquire to choose a profession, and most importantly, to find one's place in life. In today's information age, the importance of books and reading is incomparable in bringing up our young people with high morals and virtues.

It is at this time that, despite the different approaches to the implementation of students' interest in reading books in general education schools and the different forecasts about their future, scientists and pedagogues came to the same opinion that extracurricular lessons in their traditional form do not give the expected results and do not bring significant benefits. The question of what exactly is students' interest in reading books and how it can be developed becomes relevant in the field of methodical science, because the prospects of restructuring the primary course of teaching reading in grades 1-4, including the fate of extracurricular reading classes, which were allocated 123 hours in the old curriculum depends on the solution.

E. Yoldashev, one of the Uzbek librarians, is particularly noteworthy for his scientific research directly related to the problem of children's reading and cooperation between school libraries.

If an effective technology and method of forming and educating elementary school students to reading books is developed and applied, the level of effectiveness of students' rational use of books and libraries, and the formation of a reading culture will increase.

Formation of independent educational needs and abilities of readers is one of the problems that attracts everyone's attention, the importance of solving them is indisputable for everyone, and solutions can be offered by a voluntary literate person based on his experience. Is it necessary to complicate the process of teaching a child to a book, which is expressed several times in many sources and sufficiently uniformly?

"From the second half of the first year of a child's education at school, an art book enters his life - writes A.A. Lyublinskaya, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, in his research work. - The child not only listens to how adults read to him, but also begins to read. As soon as the difficulties in the reading technique are overcome, children become more interested in a new type of activity for them. By quoting this opinion of the scientist, we did not mean that the author does not understand the level of complexity of the problem that he superficially mentions.

In the collection devoted to experimental studies of the motivational spheres of children and adolescents under the editorship of V.V. Davydov: "The birth of a new need does not happen automatically... For example, a child learns to read well, knows many works of art, and feels the need to read and enrich his knowledge. we can see that he may not do it. This is a unique phenomenon emphasized by psychologists.

Reading it in accordance with the content of a suitable book creates an unmistakable impression and interest in the mind of the reader, creates further needs, encourages the will to achieve new goals, and in order to achieve them, it is necessary to communicate with the multifaceted world of information, that is, the world of books, from the space-time space of universal human activity. will need to exit. In the first option, a reading activity occurs, and the system begins to work again, assuming the form of self-activation. This variant is shown in Figure 2. Conditional signs: The book to be read and the purpose of reading determined by someone else (according

to educational, scientific or practical necessity). Having assimilated the content of what was read, the reader may feel the need to continue reading (on purpose, on the topic, etc.), or he may not feel such a need if he does not find any personal content in the process of reading the book "on obligation". In the first case, the activity of reading does not stop, but on the contrary, it has a personal content, and the reader continues according to diagram 1, according to the goal set by someone, changed according to his needs that arose in the process of reading a book, or put forward on the basis of associations. In the second case, if the motivation that prompts the reader to read the specified book disappears during reading due to the fact that the reader does not have a special personal content in front of his eyes, the activity ends with mastering the content of what was read. In other words, the component that served as the beginning in this case is also the final one in the system of personal reading activity under investigation.

Accordingly, there are no conditions for the operation of the system of independent reading activity. A "circle" is not formed, as a result of the need's "meeting" with the object that responds to it, it becomes capable of directing and controlling the activity for the first time. The meeting of the need with the object is an extraordinary act, the act of objectifying the need - "filling" it with the content taken from the surrounding world.

REFERENCES

1. Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev dated January 12, 2017 No. F-4789 "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing

interest in book reading and book reading, and promotion". // "Khalk Sozi"
newspaper, T.: January 13, 2017.